

A place of enlightenment and spirituality

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Key words: Hero of Uzbekistan, People's poet of Uzbekistan, State specialized boarding school, "Spring, mother, woman's hymn in the work of Abdullah Oripov", "The symbol of the great in the work of Abdullah Oripov", "The youngest talented poet of the year", State award named after Zulfiya, "The year the youngest talented poet", Temur's connoisseur", "Love Life" Republican pageant.

Abstract: In this article, in order to perpetuate the name of the Hero of Uzbekistan, People's Poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla Oripov, and to select talented students for in-depth study of the native language and literature among the students, and to further develop their talent, the State Specialized Boarding School named after Abdulla Oripov was established in the city of Karshi, all the activities held at the school Spiritual and educational activities are organized with the focus on students' creativity and the importance of school as a spiritual institution is shown. and abode of enlightenment.

Decision No. 312 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2017 in order to perpetuate the name of the Hero of Uzbekistan, People's Poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla Oripov and to select talented students for in-depth study of the native language and the science of literature among young students and further develop their talent[1]. Based on the order[2] and decisions of the Minister of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 176 dated May 25, 2017, the State Specialized Boarding School named after Abdulla Oripov was established in Karshi. This boarding school is equipped with the latest technologies

It has a modern [4:1492-195] educational building, a dormitory, a kitchen, a gymnasium and an activist hall for 210 seats. A huge statue of the poet stands in front of the boarding school building in a large and magnificent square named after Abdulla Oripov. On the first floor of the building, the Abdulla Oripov Museum is operating.

Currently, 161 talented and creative students are studying in this boarding school, which was accepted on the basis of competition. Among them there are students from Tashkent, Samarkand, Surkhandarya region.

All the spiritual and educational events held at the school are organized with the focus on the students' creativity. Competitions of creative [5:135-138] works dedicated to important dates are regularly held. For example, dedicated to the birthdays of the great thinker Alisher Navoi and the king and poet 3.M. Babur, "A great wisdom in every line", "Spring, mother, woman's hymn in the work of Abdullah Oripov", "The symbol of the great in the work of Abdullah Oripov", as well as Uzbek literature According to the dates of birth of prominent figures [6:1-6], the competitions of creative works held in the fields of poetry, prose, dramaturgy, music, and visual arts have given good results and are increasing the love for creativity among students. Since the establishment of the boarding school, many achievements have been made.

In 2018, the 8th-grade student of the boarding school, Omonova Sevinch, participated in the republican stage of the "Youngest Talented Poet of the Year" contest and took the proud 1st place.

In 2019, Alisherova Ezoza, a 10th grader, took part in the International Symposium [7:121-123] held in Japan based on the "Sakura science program" program, showing her artistic performances in Japanese, leaving a great impression on everyone. Uzbek,

Ezoza, who is fluent in English, Russian, Japanese, and Tajik languages, was awarded the Zulfiya State Prize by our country's president in March 2019.

In 2019, the 10th grade student Abdurayimova Mashhura won the 1st place in the poetry section of the famous "Why do I love Uzbekistan" competition and was able to participate in the republican stage. In August 2019, Mashhura took the 3rd place in the Republic contest "The Youngest Talented Poet of the Year" held in the city of Jizzakh.

In the competition dedicated to the birthday of Sahibqiron Amir Temur in the city of Shahrisabz and Yakkabog district by the administration of Kashkadarya region, 8 students of the boarding school were awarded the 1st degree diploma, certificate and motivational prizes "Temur's tuzuklari bilimdoni". They won the proud 1st place in the contest "The team that performed the national anthem of the Republic of Uzbekistan the best" held in the province.

Boarding school students won the "Zakovat" intellectual game republic tournament held by the Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan in 2019 and were awarded the "Zakovat" statuette. With "diploma" and souvenirs

In April 2020, 9th-grade student Omonova Sevinsh took the proud 2nd place in the "Love Life" republican competition, and 11th-grade student Rakhmatullaeva Nastarin was awarded a "Diploma" for her active participation.

Poetry collections "Kashkadarya bayozy", "Mitty star glitters", "Yana bahor keldi" were published in order to support the creativity of talented students of the boarding school [8:96-100]. Also, creative students Omonova Sevinch, Bobonazarov Ibrat, Abdurayimova Mashhura, Narsillaeva Maftuna, Ismatillaev

Lochinbek, Begamova Sadokat, Hamraeva Sevinch, Ravshanova Malika, Alisherova E'zoza, Sevinch Nurmatova, Ezoza Yoldosheva, Salomova Dilobar's works were published.

Well-known linguists, literary scholars, famous poets and writers of our republic at the initiative of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, as well as the regional Writers' Union. Sirojiddin Sayyid Minhajiddin Mirza, Ghairat Majid, Rustam Musurmon, Ashurali Joraev, Salim Ashur, Akhmadjon Meliboev, Khal Muhammad Hassan, Khumayun Akbar, Kazakhboy Yoldashev, Fakhridin Hayit, Nurboy Jabbarov, Mahmud Toir, Ikram Atamurod, Farugat Khudoykulova, Saydi Umirov, Luqman Borikhan. , Jabbor Eshonqul, Sirojiddin Rauf, Norqabil Jalil, Enakhon Siddiqova, Ma'mura Zohidova, Bakhtiyor Genjamurod, as well as in accordance with the contract concluded with Karshi State University, N. Shodmonov, B. Bakhridinova of the "Uzbek Linguistics" and "Literature" department of the university, "Skills lesson" was held at a high level with literary and linguist scholars such as N.Musulmanova, Sh.Kahhorova, honorary teachers, oasis creators.

"Motherland and Independence [9:128-131] hymn in Abdullah Oripov's poetry" devoted to the life and work of Abdulla Oripov in the series "Uzbekistan - My Country" in cooperation with the regional television and radio company, "The incomparable role of Abdulla Oripov's work in human spiritual maturity", "Abdulla Oripov In the memory of contemporaries", "Abdullah Oripov's special role in the translation of Uzbek literature" were prepared and aired programs with the participation of school teachers and students. Also, "Uzbekistan 24", "Sevimli", "Youth", "Enlightenment and Spirituality", "My country" , "Uzbekistan", "Dunyo Buylab" TV channels,

boarding school activity and talent programs about students were given. 24 of 2018 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Paragraph 57 of the "Measures program for the comprehensive development of tourism in Kashkadarya region" approved by March decision No. 24/338 [3], starting from May 9, 2019, the "Golden Word" international literature festival dedicated to the memory of Abdulla Oripov will be held once a year. The 1st International Literature Festival was held on May 8, 2019, in cooperation with the Kashkadarya Regional Government, the Regional Department of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the State Specialized Boarding School named after A. Oripov. Sengeli Bilgi, president of the international literary organization "Kibatek" in Turkey, Leyla Isik, vice-president of the organization, Epitasio Tongohan, president of the international literary organization "Pentasi V" in the Philippines, employee of the Intercontinental Culture Association of India, writer Solomiya Karoli, Italian poet, writer took part in the festival events. and bloggers Katirino Davinio, Claudio Preziosi, Toshmat Temirov, editor-in-chief of "Dostlik" and "Elchi" newspapers in Tajikistan, Zebiniso Sattorova, professor of Kurgantepa State University named after Nasir Khusrav, Hasan Goyib, member of the Writers' Union of Tajikistan, Maisara Saparova, reporter of "South Kazakhstan" newspaper, "Chimkent" in Kazakhstan Erkinoy Sultonovalar, the chairman of the creative association, Shahnoza Jalilova, reporter of "Elchi" newspaper, and poetess visited.

Among the guests, Sengeli Bilgi, Epitasio Tangohan, Katirina Davinio, Claudio Preziosi and Hasan Ghayib spoke and gave their gifts to the boarding school students.

Boarding school Good school participating in the project d took the proud 2nd place in the republic and was awarded with a "Diploma" and a valuable gift from the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Cooperation with all creative schools established in our republic is well established. On April 24-27, 2018 and April 27, 2019, the teachers and students of the boarding school actively participated in events dedicated to the birthday of the famous poet Muhammad Yusuf. In April 2018, H. Olimjon and Zulfiya school management in Jizzakh visited our school. Also, the teachers of our school went to this school [10:396-400] and shared their experience [13].

In one article, Abdulla Oripov asked the journalist "How do you imagine Uzbek literature in the 21st century as a famous poet of our nation?" answered the question: "You know very well the saying of one of our great teachers, Abdulla Qahhor, that "Uzbek literature will be a great literature in the future." If I interpret this quality in my own way, this literature will be truly folkloric, bright as a rainbow, bright as a diamond, clear as a crystal, beautiful in all respects, truly artistic literature. It will be such an art of words that the people of the world will see the words of an Uzbek before themselves, and this is an "Uzbek miracle". I am sure that the future of literature and art, which has the possibility of development [12:26-28], will be bright."

The days have come when the poet said with confidence! Today, foreigners are more and more interested in the works of poets, Uzbek literature, and classic works of art. We witnessed this clearly at the International Literature Festival held at our school.

In fact, creative schools founded on the initiative of the head of our state, Sh. Mirziyoev, are literally a product of New Goya. This idea envisages the noble goal of raising the spirituality of our people, our nation to higher heights, bringing honor to the name of the Motherland like the great ancestors. After all, it is inevitable that a good goal will bring good results.

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